

Thermal conductivity of silica refractories and its temperature dependence during thermal cycling, compared to silicite and sandstone

Lucie Kotrbová^{a,*}, Tereza Uhlířová^a, Willi Pabst^a, Jana Hubálková^b, Miroslav Kotouček^c

^a Department of Glass and Ceramics, University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague, (UCT Prague), Technická 5, 166 28 Prague 6, Czech Republic

^b Institute of Ceramics, Refractories and Composites, Technische Universität Bergakademie Freiberg, Agricolastrasse 17, 09599 Freiberg, Germany

^c RHI Magnesita Czech Republic a.s., Průmyslová 424/13, 268 02 Svitavy, Czech Republic

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Silica refractories (tridymite, cristobalite)
Thermal conductivity
Thermal diffusivity
Laser-flash technique
Silica-based rocks (silicite, sandstone)

ABSTRACT

The thermophysical properties of silica refractories are important for their potential application as high-temperature thermal energy storage (HT-TES) media. In this paper, we report new measurements of thermal conductivity and thermal diffusivity by plane-source techniques and the laser-flash technique, respectively. The latter is also used to determine the temperature dependence of the thermal conductivity from room temperature to 800 °C during heating and cooling. It is shown that for a silica refractory with porosity 21 % the experimentally measured thermal conductivity (1.3–1.6 W/mK) is significantly lower than the analytical and numerical predictions for spherical, polyhedral and concave pores (3.1–4.7 W/mK), which indicates the influence of microcracks. The anomaly in the temperature dependence below ~200 °C can be attributed to the phase transitions of cristobalite and tridymite, but above this temperature the thermal conductivity increases, whereas that of silicite and sandstone decreases. Thermal cycling leads to microcrack-induced damage.

1. Introduction

Silica refractories are traditional refractories for certain niche applications, in some of which they are irreplaceable. Apart from coke ovens constructions and glass melter roofs, which are the most widespread applications, silica refractories are being traditionally used in hot blast stoves (regenerators or recuperators) for dome constructions and, more importantly in our context, as a thermo-accumulative filling (so-called “checker-work”, made of “checker-bricks”) in the upper parts of the hot blast stove [1–6]. Silica refractories have also been used in regenerators and recuperators of the glass industry [6], although the use in this context is somewhat restricted for two reasons: first, they should be used only for temperatures higher than 1470 °C in this specific context (because alkaline vapors easily react with tridymite, leading to corrosion, while cristobalite remains unaffected by alkaline vapors) and second, they should only be used in oxidizing environments (to avoid SiO formation), while glass producers usually prefer reducing environments to reduce NO_x emissions [7]. However, for modern high-temperature thermal energy storage (HT-TES) of solar energy the latter corrosion problems are irrelevant. In this application the material is to be heated electrically (through tubular channels in the refractory block checker-work), and for this purpose it is an advantage that silica

refractories have a high degree of spectral emission at wavelengths above 5 μm (higher than ~90 % from 5 μm up to ~14 μm), essentially independent of temperature and surface roughness [8].

For all these applications, but especially for modern high-temperature thermal energy storage (HT-TES) of solar energy, where thermal cycling is an essential mode of operation, it is important to know the mechanical, thermomechanical and thermal properties (or behavior) of the material as a function of the temperature during thermal cycling. While the temperature dependence and cycling performance of the elastic properties (Young's modulus), as well as the temperature dependence of the thermal expansion and creep, of silica refractories have obtained considerable attention in the literature today [9–17], and the temperature dependence of the specific heat is available from different literature sources, much less is known about the temperature dependence of the thermal conductivity of silica refractories. In particular, although the recent work of Yang et al. [18] presents a nice investigation of the thermal conductivity mechanism in silica refractories, we are not aware of any study that presents the temperature dependence and thermal cycling behavior of the thermal conductivity of silica refractories in a continuous manner (or, in other words, with sufficiently fine temperature resolution), so that the effects of the phase transitions between the low- and high-temperature modifications of

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: lucie.kotrbova@vscht.cz (L. Kotrbová).

cristobalite and tridymite can be seen in a similar way as for elastic properties. The present work intends to fill this gap. Fig. 1 shows a summary of literature data [3,4,19,20] for the thermal conductivity of silica refractories as a function of temperature. It is evident that the thermal conductivity is a strong function of the bulk density and ranges from values around 0.5 W/mK for insulating light-weight silica bricks (porosities of ~40–65 %) and values higher than 1 W/mK for normal-density silica bricks (porosity around 20 %) to values higher than 2 W/mK for superdense silica bricks (with porosities lower than 15 %). Recent laser-flash measurements for samples of different thickness at selected temperatures [19] are in good agreement with these literature data and show in the low-temperature region (below 300 °C) clear indications of phase transitions and of damage after cooling. Most intriguing, however, is the generally increasing trend of the thermal conductivity of silica refractories with temperature, which is highly unusual for other polycrystalline materials.

A complication for predicting the thermal conductivity of silica refractories is the fact that the thermal conductivities of the main phases, cristobalite and tridymite, are not reliably known even at room temperature. To the best of our knowledge, the only value available for cristobalite is the value 6.15 W/mK (at room temperature) obtained by an atomistic *ab initio* simulation [21]. For tridymite, not even such a value is available. From the viewpoint of experimental work, another complication comes into play, when the laser-flash technique is used: since the primary result of the laser-flash technique is the thermal diffusivity, the specific heat is needed to obtain thermal conductivity values. Fortunately, as mentioned above, quite reliable specific heat values are available in the literature as functions of temperature for cristobalite [22,23], tridymite [22,23] and pseudowollastonite [24], while the glass phase can in a first approximation be assumed to be close to silica glass, for which all these data are known [25]. Except for the discrepancies of the transition temperatures that can lead to artefacts in the temperature dependence of the calculated thermal conductivity, these literature data of specific heat, which are quite similar for all silica phases [26], and are – with slight adaptations as discussed in the present paper – fully sufficient for determining the thermal conductivity from thermal diffusivity data.

In order to validate the methodology of this paper and to emphasize the very specific character of the temperature dependence of the thermal

conductivity of silica refractories, the results for silica refractories are compared in this paper with those of other silica-based materials (natural rocks), namely silicite and sandstone. In contrast to silica refractories, the latter have lower porosity and do not contain cristobalite or tridymite but are based on quartz (with a few other minerals in small quantities in the sandstone). Since the thermal properties of quartz are well known, these results lead to a deeper understanding of the measurement results and their comparison with analytical and numerical predictions. Moreover, at room temperature, the (contact-less) laser-flash results are compared with results from (contact-based) modified transient plane source methods, in order to assess the reliability and accuracy of the experimental data. The Experimental and Modeling sections following this Introduction present the details of the applied methodology, while the Results and discussion section presents (always in the sequence silica refractory, silicite, sandstone) first, for room temperature, the comparison of analytical and numerical predictions with the experimental results (including the mutual comparison of experimental data obtained from different transient techniques) and second, the temperature dependence of the thermal conductivity during heating and cooling (thermal cycling), which is again highlighted in the Summary and conclusions section.

2. Experimental details

The silica refractories investigated in this work have been produced by P-D Refractories CZ, a.s. (now RHI Magnesita Czech Republic, a.s.) and contain 47.5 wt.% tridymite, 44.7 wt.% cristobalite, 6.0 wt.% pseudowollastonite, 1.8 wt.% glass phase (solid phases summing up to 100 wt.%) and 21 vol.% porosity (i.e. 79 vol.% of solid phases). Further details concerning the chemical and phase composition as well as the microstructure of these silica refractories can be found elsewhere [16, 17]. The silicite sample has been collected in the Bulizník belt near Kladno (Czech Republic) and contains 100 wt.% quartz (with tiny amounts of accessory mineral which are undetectable by X-ray diffraction) and 1.8 % porosity. The sandstone sample has been collected in the Buntsandstein formation at Freudenstadt (Germany) and contains 79.9 wt.% quartz, 10.1 wt.% muscovite, 9.4 wt.% microcline, 0.6 wt.% hematite and 12 % porosity. The phase composition and porosity of these natural rock materials has been taken from Kotrbová's master thesis

Fig. 1. Thermal conductivity of silica refractories as a function of temperature; data from the literature [3,4,19,20]; the three data sets for density 1.832 g/cm³ [19] are the results of recent laser-flash measurements for samples with different thickness (2.6 mm – red, 3.6 mm – orange, 4.3 mm – yellow) and the difference in the room temperature values before heating and after cooling is due to thermal-cycling-induced damage (microcracking).

[27]. In all cases the phase composition has been determined via X-ray diffraction, while the (total) porosity has been calculated from the bulk density determined via the Archimedes principle and the true density calculated from the phase composition. For the laser-flash measurements, small specimens with square cross sections of approximately 10×10 mm have been prepared, see Fig. 2. The modified transient plane source (MTPS) measurements were performed (with two different instruments, ISOMET 2114 / Applied Precision, Slovakia and TRIDENT / C-Therm, Canada) on planar sections of sufficiently large samples with a thickness of several cm (so that they can, from the viewpoint of the one-dimensional heat flux, be considered as semi-infinite), see Fig. 3.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) of the silica refractory has been performed with an Empyrean Series 3 diffractometer (Malvern PANalytical, The Netherlands), using $\text{CoK}\alpha$ radiation. Quantitative phase analysis was performed via Rietveld refinement [28], using the HighScorePlus software package version 5.2.0 (Malvern PANalytical, The Netherlands) [29] and the PDF-5+ database [30]. The amorphous phase content has been determined via the internal standard method [31], using ZnO as an internal standard. Dilatometric measurements have been performed in air on a DIL 402 C dilatometer (Netzsch, Germany) during heating from room temperature to 800°C with a heating rate of 5 K/min .

The laser-flash measurements [32] were performed using a laser-flash analyzer (LFA 1000, Linseis, Germany) from room temperature to 800°C and back to room temperature (during heating and cooling). For this purpose, all samples (with square cross section of dimensions 10×10 mm) were coated on both surfaces (front and rear side of the specimen) by a graphite layer (Kontaktchemie® Graphite 33, CRC Industries Europe, Belgium). After a short (< 1 ms) laser pulse (from an Nd:YAG laser with wavelength 1064 nm) hits the front side, a signal proportional to the relative temperature increase on the rear side is registered by a liquid-nitrogen-cooled In-Sb infrared detector. The basic relation for extracting the thermal diffusivity a from the half-time $t_{1/2}$ of the temperature rise on the rear surface of the specimen is Parker's relation [33] for infinitely short laser pulses and adiabatic conditions,

$$a = 0.1388 \frac{h^2}{t_{1/2}}, \quad (1)$$

where h is the sample thickness. However, in the present work a more

Fig. 2. Silica refractory sample of dimensions $10 \times 10 \times 2.5$ mm for the laser-flash measurements (before coating with graphite).

sophisticated combined model is often used that takes into account the finite laser pulse duration and heat losses across the side faces of the sample (Dusza's model) [34]. All laser flash measurements in this work have been performed in vacuum, using a "dynamic" (quasi-continuous) mode of measurement during thermal cycling (heating and cooling) with rates changing from 0.5 to 5 K/min , i.e. laser-flash measurements were performed during heating and cooling, and for data evaluation the baseline slope has been taken into account during curve fitting. The sample thickness for these measurements was ~ 2.5 mm (range 2.44 – 2.53 mm). Measurements have been performed for one sample of each type and cycling maximum temperature (i.e. in the case of the silica refractory one sample has been used for cycling to 800°C and another one for cycling to 300°C). Although in the case of the silica refractory the sample thickness of 2.5 mm is of the same order of magnitude as the grain size (which could in principle raise concerns whether the value measured for one sample is sufficiently representative for the material), it has been shown in a recent paper [19] that the sample-to-sample variability is actually smaller than the effect of the increased radiation losses for thicker samples (meaning that thicker samples yield systematically lower thermal diffusivity values due to higher radiation losses in the transverse direction). The surprisingly good consistency of the measured thermal diffusivity values despite the heterogeneity of the silica refractory samples is probably caused by the incidental fact that the thermal diffusivity values of cristobalite and tridymite are very similar.

The thermal conductivity k is then calculated from the thermal diffusivity a , using the bulk density ρ and the specific heat c_p of the material, according to the relation

$$k = a \cdot \rho \cdot c_p. \quad (2)$$

The temperature-dependent specific heat data for this calculation have been taken from the literature, see below, while the temperature-dependent bulk density has been calculated from the bulk density measured via the Archimedes principle at room temperature and the thermal expansion measured dilatometrically. When σ_L is the relative length change (compared to the sample dimensions at room temperature as a reference), the relation for calculating the bulk density as a function of temperature is

$$\rho(T) = \frac{\rho(20^\circ\text{C})}{(1 + \sigma_L)^3}. \quad (3)$$

In addition to the laser-flash measurements, modified transient plane source (MTPS) measurements [35] of the thermal conductivity were performed (at room temperature only) with two instruments: ISOMET 2114 (Applied Precision, Slovakia) and TRIDENT (C-Therm, Canada). These methods, which use factory-calibrated sensors, provide the thermal conductivity directly.

3. Modeling approach

Based on the mass fractions w_i of the individual phases, as determined via X-ray diffraction / XRD, and the theoretical densities of the individual phases, ρ_i , taken from the literature (including the true density of the glass phase, assumed here to be a pure silica glass), the weight fractions of the individual phases can be transformed into volume fractions φ_i ,

$$\varphi_i = \frac{w_i / \rho_i}{\sum w_i / \rho_i}. \quad (4)$$

and the effective true density of the dense, i.e. non-porous material ρ_0 can be calculated via the volume-weighted mixture rule

$$\rho_0 = \sum \varphi_i \rho_i. \quad (5)$$

Based on this value and the bulk density ρ determined by the

Fig. 3. Silica refractory samples for the modified transient plane source (MTPS) measurements (left: ISOMET 2114, right: TRIDENT).

Archimedes method, the total porosity can be calculated via the relation

$$\varphi = 1 - \frac{\rho}{\rho_0}. \quad (6)$$

Similarly, the effective specific heat, required for transforming the thermal diffusivity into thermal conductivity according to Eq. (2), is calculated according to the mass-weighted mixture rule

$$c_p = \sum w_i c_{pi}. \quad (7)$$

The effective thermal conductivity of the dense, i.e. non-porous, material, k_0 , can be estimated via the simple arithmetic mean of the upper and lower Wiener bounds, i.e. the volume-weighted arithmetic and harmonic means [36,37]

$$k_0 = \frac{1}{2} \left[\sum \varphi_i k_i + \left(\sum \frac{\varphi_i}{k_i} \right)^{-1} \right], \quad (8)$$

where the φ_i are the phase volume fractions, the k_i are the phase conductivities and k_0 is the effective thermal conductivity of the dense material. As soon as the latter value is reliably established, the porosity dependence can be taken into account via theoretical bounds [36,37] like the upper Wiener bound,

$$k \leq k_0 (1 - \varphi), \quad (9)$$

and the upper Hashin-Shtrikman bound,

$$k \leq k_0 \left(\frac{1 - \varphi}{1 + \varphi/2} \right), \quad (10)$$

or via analytical model predictions [36,37] like the power-law relation,

$$k = k_0 (1 - \varphi)^{3/2}, \quad (11)$$

and the exponential relation,

$$k = k_0 \exp \left(\frac{-\frac{3}{2}\varphi}{1 - \varphi} \right), \quad (12)$$

where φ is the pore volume fraction (porosity) and the k is the effective thermal conductivity of the porous material.

Apart from this analytical modeling approach, numerical modeling is possible. In the present work, the commercial software package

GeoDict® (Math2Market, Germany) has been used for generating “proxies” of the real materials, i.e. random microstructures with isotropic grains and spherical, polyhedral or concave pores, exclusively based on the phase volume fractions and porosity as input information, see Table 1. In a second step, the effective thermal conductivity has been calculated for these computer-generated “proxies”, based on the thermal conductivities of the individual phases, see also Table 1. The base models were prepared using the “Pack Analytic Spheres” algorithm from the “GrainGeo” module, consisting of 1000 spheres of the same size and a target solid volume fraction of 0.63. The domain was set as periodic (i.e. with periodic boundaries), with dimensions of $500 \times 500 \times 500$ voxels.

The model with polyhedral pores (proxy B) included all phases (including pores as a separate phase), all set to their corresponding volume fractions, calculated according to Eq. (4), and was subsequently fully “sintered” to 100 % virtual density (i.e. including the pore phase) using the “GrainGeoSinter” algorithm from the same module (“GrainGeo”). The model with concave pore shape (proxy C) was prepared in a similar way, but only the solid phases were included, and it was “sintered” only partially, in order to achieve a density of 79 % (thus leaving the total porosity listed in Table 2 below). For the model with spherical pores (proxy A), generated using the “Create Grains” algorithm of the “GrainGeo” module, the effective thermal conductivity of the dense material has been calculated in a first step for a fully sintered material consisting only of solid phases. Isolated spheres with a diameter of 50 voxels were then inserted into this “homogenized” material with a porosity listed in Table 2. Each type of model and material was prepared 10 times with different random seeds.

Thermal conductivity tensor calculations have been performed via the GeoDict® ConductoDict module (with a solver based on the so-called explicit jump immersed interface method [38,39]), using periodic boundary conditions on the (periodic) boundaries of the computer-generated microstructures. After calculation of the tensor components and checking the isotropy, orientational averaging has been performed for all 10 realizations of the random microstructures, so that the resulting effective thermal conductivity is an average of $10 \times 3 = 30$ individual tensor component values. These calculations are based on literature values as input information and have been performed only for room temperature.

3. Results and discussion

Table 1 lists the phase composition in wt.% (as determined by XRD),

Table 1

Phase composition in wt.% (as determined by XRD), densities of the individual phases (assuming the glass phase to be a pure silica glass), phase composition in vol.% (calculated on the basis of the individual densities via Eq. (4)) and specific heats and thermal conductivities of the individual phases (from the literature [27,40–42], the value for tridymite being an estimate).

Sample	Solid phase	Phase content [wt. %]	Theoretical density [g/cm ³]	Phase content [vol. %]	Specific heat [J/gK]	Thermal conductivity [W/mK]
Silica refractory	Tridymite	47.5	2.26	48.7	0.745	6.00
	Cristobalite	44.7	2.32	44.6	0.745	6.15
	Pseudowollastonite	6.0	2.91	4.8	0.753	4.50
	Silica glass	1.8	2.20	1.9	0.737	1.38
Silicite	Quartz	100	2.65	100	0.745	7.9
Sandstone	Quartz	79.9	2.65	80.4	0.745	7.9
	Muscovite	10.1	2.83	9.5	0.780	2.1
	Microcline	9.4	2.57	9.7	0.730	2.4
	Hematite	0.6	5.26	0.3	0.649	11.6

Table 2

True density (calculated via volume fractions), bulk density and open porosity (determined by the Archimedes method), total porosity (calculated from the relative density, i.e. the ratio of bulk density and true density, via Eq. (6)), specific heat of the dense material (calculated via the weight fractions via Eq. (7)) and thermal conductivity of the dense material (calculated as the simple arithmetic mean of the upper and lower Wiener bounds, see Eq. (8)).

	True density [g/cm ³]	Bulk density [g/cm ³]	Open porosity [%]	Total porosity [%]	Specific heat [J/gK]	Thermal conductivity [W/mK]
Silica refractory	2.31	1.83	21.0	21.0	0.745	5.90
Silicite	2.65	2.60	–	1.8	0.745	7.90
Sandstone	2.67	2.35	10.2	12.0	0.747	6.83

theoretical densities of the individual phases (assuming the glass phase to be a pure silica glass), phase composition in vol.% (calculated on the basis of the individual phase densities) as well as specific heats and thermal conductivities of the individual phases (from the literature [27, 40–42]) for the silica refractory, sandstone and silicite investigated in this work. All these values are for room temperature. Unfortunately, in contrast to quartz, (pseudo-)wollastonite, microcline, mica, hematite and silica glass, experimental data for the thermal conductivity of pure cristobalite and tridymite are practically non-existent in the literature and therefore our value for cristobalite is based on an atomistic *ab-initio* simulation [21] and that for tridymite is an estimate, based the fact that the density of tridymite is slightly lower than that of cristobalite (but much lower than that of quartz) and assuming a simple correlation between thermal conductivity and density, similar to the correlation found for the different silica polymorphs between Young's modulus and density [26]. All other thermal conductivity values in Table 1 have been obtained from the thermal conductivity tensor components of the corresponding single crystals by calculating the simple arithmetic mean of the upper and lower Molyneux bounds [43] (or, in the case of uniaxial crystals, the more precise Hashin-Shtrikman bounds [44]), assuming that the crystallites are randomly oriented, i.e. the polycrystalline

materials are statistically isotropic. It is evident that at room temperature the crystalline silica phases (quartz, cristobalite, tridymite) have a higher thermal conductivity than the other phases (except for hematite, which is contained in the sandstone investigated here in very small amounts, < 1 %).

Table 2 lists the true density (calculated as the volume-weighted arithmetic mean of the phase densities), bulk density and open porosity (both determined by the Archimedes method), total porosity (calculated from the relative density, i.e. the ratio of bulk density and true density), the specific heat of the dense material (calculated via the mass-weighted arithmetic mean) and the thermal conductivity of the dense material (calculated as the arithmetic mean of the upper and lower Wiener bounds). The corresponding relations for calculating these values have been given above.

Based on the phase composition and (total) porosity, computer-generated digital proxies with three different types of random microstructures have been prepared for each material, as explained in the previous section. Typical examples of these digital proxies are shown in Figs. 4, 5 and 6 for the silica refractory, silicite and sandstone, respectively. It has to be emphasized that these digital proxies are not meant to represent the real microstructure of the corresponding materials in all

Fig. 4. Digital proxies of the silica refractory with three different random microstructures: polycrystalline multiphase with spherical (A – left), polyhedral (B – middle) and concave (C – right) pores, respectively; tridymite – green, cristobalite – red, pseudowollastonite – blue, silica glass – yellow, homogenized mixture of all solid phases – grey.

Fig. 5. Digital proxies of silicite with three different random microstructures: polycrystalline single-phase with spherical (A – left), polyhedral (B – middle) and concave (C – right) pores, respectively; homogenized mixture of all solid phases – grey.

Fig. 6. Digital proxies of sandstone with three different random microstructures: polycrystalline multiphase with spherical (A – left), polyhedral (B – middle) and concave (C – right) pores, respectively; quartz – red, muscovite – yellow, microcline – green, hematite – blue, homogenized mixture of all solid phases – grey.

details (which are usually not available anyway, at least not in quantitative form to be implemented in the computer algorithm to generate the proxies) but are just virtual model materials with the same phase composition and porosity, i.e. the minimum information on the

microstructure. Based on these digital proxies and the thermal conductivity of the individual phases as input information (see Table 1), the effective thermal conductivity has been numerically calculated, as explained in the previous section, and can now be compared with

Fig. 7. Thermal conductivity of the silica refractory according to analytical predictions (upper Wiener bound, upper Hashin-Shtrikman bound, power-law relation, exponential relation), numerical predictions with three different pore shapes (spherical, polyhedral, concave) and experimental measurements with three different instruments (ISOMET, TRIDENT, LFA1000); all values at room temperature.

analytical predictions and experimental data.

Figs. 7, 8 and 9 show the room temperature values of the thermal conductivity for the silica refractory, silicite and sandstone, respectively, according to analytical predictions (upper Wiener bound, upper Hashin-Shtrikman bound, power-law relation, exponential relation), numerical predictions with three different pore shapes (spherical, polyhedral, concave) and experimental measurements with three different instruments (ISOMET, TRIDENT, LFA1000). The analytical predictions for the effective thermal conductivity of the materials have been calculated on the basis of the thermal conductivity of the dense materials and the (total) porosity listed in Table 2 according to the aforementioned relations, Eqs. (9)–(12). It is evident that in all cases the numerical results are lower than the upper Hashin-Shtrikman bounds, as required for physically meaningful data (numerical or experimental). Moreover, from Fig. 7 it is evident that for the silica refractory with porosity 21 % the experimentally measured thermal conductivity (1.3–1.6 W/mK) is significantly lower than the analytical predictions and the numerical predictions for spherical, polyhedral and concave pores (3.1–4.7 W/mK). This is a consequence of the fact that neither the analytical relations nor the numerical modeling take into account the microcracks that can be present in the material. Microcracks can be considered as extremely flat (oblate) pores. In contrast to isometric pores, whose influence on the thermal conductivity is low when the porosity (pore volume fraction) is low, the influence of microcracks on the thermal conductivity can be large even if their volume fraction is negligibly small. In other words, the low experimental values (which are mutually very consistent) indicate that a considerable amount of microcracks is present in the silica refractory. A qualitatively similar conclusion holds also for silicite and sandstone, but in these cases the relative difference between the predictions and the experimental values is less severe, so that the experimental values are closer to the predictions (relative differences less than 26 % for the silicite and less than 151 % for the sandstone, but up to 265 % for the silica refractory). Although this is only indirect evidence of the presence of microcracks, direct evidence has been recently provided for the same silica refractories by mercury porosimetry [17], and it has to be recalled that also the increase of Young's modulus during heating and its decrease during cooling is commonly explained by the closure and re-opening of pre-existent

microcracks [16,17]. In principle, in the case of silica refractories an alternative explanation of the discrepancy between model predictions and experimentally measured data would be the hypothesis that the glass phase covers all grains, i.e. is present on the grain boundaries rather than along triple junctions or at quadruple nodes. Both analytical and numerical modeling could be modified to take this into account. This would indeed reduce the predicted values, so that better agreement between model predictions and experimental values would be achieved. However, recent scanning electron microscopy studies [17] do not substantiate this hypothesis for the silica refractories investigated here.

For obtaining the thermal conductivity as a function of temperature from the laser-flash measurements, the temperature dependence of the bulk density and specific heat is required as an input information. While the temperature dependence of the bulk density can simply be calculated from thermal expansion data, see Eq. (3), that of the specific heat requires quite complex measurements, which are considerably complicated by the (displacive, i.e. fast and reversible) phase transitions of the silica polymorphs (quartz, cristobalite, tridymite) between their low- and high-temperature modifications (subpolymorphs). For our purpose we calculate the bulk density data from thermal expansion data measured for this work but take the specific heat data from the literature. The corresponding graphs are shown in Fig. 10 for the silica refractory (calculated via Eq. (7) on the basis of the temperature dependences of the specific heats for cristobalite, tridymite, pseudowollastonite and silica glass, as explained below and in Appendix A [22–24]), in Fig. 11 for the silicite (i.e. for quartz only [22]) and in Fig. 12 for the sandstone (calculated via Eq. (7) on the basis of the temperature dependences of the specific heats for quartz, muscovite, microcline and hematite, as explained in Appendix A). It is evident that changes in slope (kinks) and discontinuities appear in the temperature dependences of the bulk density and specific heat, respectively, due to phase transitions from low- to high-temperature silica phases. However, due to the polycrystalline character and impurities of the samples investigated here, the temperatures at which these effects occur in the measured thermal diffusivity and bulk density for our materials (approximately 550–570 °C for quartz, 90 °C for tridymite, and 208 and 194 °C for cristobalite during heating and cooling, respectively according to thermal diffusivity and 540–575 °C for quartz, 112 and 150

Fig. 8. Thermal conductivity of silicite according to analytical predictions (upper Wiener bound, upper Hashin-Shtrikman bound, power-law relation, exponential relation), numerical predictions with three different pore shapes (spherical, polyhedral, concave) and experimental measurements with three different instruments (ISOMET, TRIDENT, LFA1000); all values at room temperature.

Fig. 9. Thermal conductivity of sandstone according to analytical predictions (upper Wiener bound, upper Hashin-Shtrikman bound, power-law relation, exponential relation), numerical predictions with three different pore shapes (spherical, polyhedral, concave) and experimental measurements with three different instruments (ISOMET, TRIDENT, LFA1000); all values at room temperature.

Fig. 10. Bulk density (calculated from thermal expansion data via Eq. (3)) and specific heat of the silica refractory (calculated via Eq. (7), using Eqs. (13)–(16) for the individual phases [22–24]) as a function of temperature.

°C for tridymite, and 235 and 200 °C for cristobalite during heating and cooling, respectively according to bulk density [17]) do not exactly correspond to the traditional textbook values (573 °C for quartz, 117 °C for tridymite and 200 and 270 °C for cristobalite during heating and cooling, respectively [26]). Therefore, in order not to introduce computational artefacts, e.g. artificial steps, into the temperature dependence of the thermal conductivity calculated via Eq. (2), the temperature dependences of the specific heat, based on literature values, have been carefully (re-)fitted as explained in detail in Appendix A. The fit relations used in this work for silica refractories are based on the data of Thompson and Wennemer [23] for the silica polymorphs tridymite and cristobalite, the data of Parks and Kelley [24] for

pseudowollastonite, for all of which new fits have been made, and the fit relation given by Salmang and Scholze [22] for silica glass. Thus, the fit relations used in this work for the silica refractory are for tridymite (low- and high-temperature, new fit of data by Thompson and Wennemer [23], see Appendix A),

$$c_p(T) = 1.068 + 0.1035 \cdot 10^{-3} T - 0.2481 \cdot 10^5 / T^2, \quad (13)$$

for cristobalite (low- and high-temperature, new fit of data by Thompson and Wennemer [23], see Appendix A),

$$c_p(T) = 1.002 + 0.2560 \cdot 10^{-3} T - 0.3122 \cdot 10^5 / T^2, \quad (14)$$

Fig. 11. Bulk density (calculated from thermal expansion data via Eq. (3)) and specific heat of the silicite (from Eqs. (17) and 18 for quartz [22]) as a function of temperature.

Fig. 12. Bulk density (calculated from measured thermal expansion data via Eq. (3)) and specific heat of the sandstone (calculated via Eq. (7), using Eqs. (17)–(22) for the individual phases [22,45–47]) as a function of temperature.

for pseudowollastonite (new fit of data by Parks and Kelley [24]),

$$c_p(T) = 0.9121 + 0.1708 \cdot 10^{-3} T - 0.1851 \cdot 10^5 / T^2, \quad (15)$$

for silica glass (fit relation given by Salmang and Scholze [22]),

$$c_p(T) = 0.9315 + 0.2562 \cdot 10^{-3} T - 0.2402 \cdot 10^5 / T^2. \quad (16)$$

The fit relations used in this work for the mineral phases of silicite and sandstone are

$$c_p(T) = 0.7310 + 0.6460 \cdot 10^{-3} T - 0.1608 \cdot 10^5 / T^2, \quad (17)$$

for low-quartz (below 573 °C) [22],

$$c_p(T) = 0.9802 + 0.1671 \cdot 10^{-3} T, \quad (18)$$

for high-quartz (above 573 °C) [22],

$$c_p(T) = 2.3017 - 0.2034 \cdot 10^{-3} T + 7.1079 \cdot 10^3 / T^2 - 25.959 \sqrt{T}, \quad (19)$$

for muscovite [45],

$$c_p(T) = 2.7288 - 0.7800 \cdot 10^{-3} T + 1.7084 \cdot 10^4 / T^2 - 34.229 \sqrt{T} + 0.2311 \cdot 10^{-7} T^2, \quad (20)$$

for microcline [46], and

$$c_p(T) = 9.4024 - 7.6060 \cdot 10^{-3}T + 0.8844 \cdot 10^5 / T^2 + 3.5632 \cdot 10^{-6}T^2, \quad (21)$$

$$c_p(T) = -6.8614 + 1.7075 \cdot 10^{-3}T - 6.4118 \cdot 10^5 / T^2 + 212.66\sqrt{T} \quad (22)$$

for hematite at temperatures lower and higher than 677 °C, respectively [47]. All these fit relations yield specific heats in units [J/gK], with the temperature to be inserted in units [K]. Note that some of these fit relations are new, while for others the fit relations for the high-temperature polymorphs have been extrapolated to the phase transition temperatures determined in the present work, see Appendix A.

Figs. 13, 14 and 15 show the temperature dependence of thermal diffusivity for the silica refractory, silicite and sandstone, respectively, measured continuously during heating and cooling. These are the primary results from the laser flash measurements. On the other hand, Figs. 16, 17 and 18 show the temperature dependence of thermal conductivity for the silica refractory, silicite and sandstone, respectively, i.e. the secondary results obtained by combining the temperature dependences of the thermal diffusivity via Eq. (2), see Figs. 13, 14 and 15, with those of the bulk density and specific heat, see Figs. 10, 11 and 12. Fig. 19 shows an overall comparison of the thermal conductivities of the silica refractory, silicite and sandstone in one single graph with a single scale.

It is immediately evident that at room temperature both the thermal diffusivity and the thermal conductivity of silica refractories is significantly lower than the corresponding properties of silicite and sandstone. This is plausible because the porosity of the silica refractory (21 %) is much higher than that of silicite (2 %) and sandstone (12 %). However, at higher temperature and after thermal cycling this situation changes. In particular, at temperatures above the cristobalite transition (~235 °C) the thermal diffusivity of the silica refractory stabilizes at values that are slightly lower than at room temperature (0.9 mm²/s at 20 °C, but 0.8 mm²/s at 235 °C and 800 °C), while for the thermal conductivity they are higher than at room temperature and have a clearly increasing trend (1.3 W/mK at 20 °C, 1.4 W/mK at 235 °C and 1.6 W/mK at 800 °C), whereas the values for silicite and sandstone exhibit a quasi-hyperbolic decrease, which is typical for crystalline solids, and attain relatively low

values above the temperature of the quartz transition (~573 °C), approaching 0.4–0.6 mm²/s and 1.0–2.0 W/mK, respectively, at 800 °C. That means, the advantage of a higher thermal conductivity at room temperature for silicite and sandstone can be easily lost at higher temperatures, and silica refractories can be equally good thermal conductors at high temperatures as other materials that have a higher thermal conductivity at room temperature. It has to be emphasized, however, that an increase in thermal conductivity with increasing temperature (which is well known for silica refractories) is for polycrystalline materials highly unusual. Therefore, we surmise that this increase is related to the closure of microcracks during heating, which is the widely accepted explanation for the (equally unusual) increase of Young's modulus during heating [48–51].

The explanation for the anomalous temperature dependence of the thermal conductivity of the silica refractories in the vicinity of the phase transitions between the low- and high-temperature subpolymorphs of tridymite and cristobalite is highly non-trivial. At least two aspects have to be taken into account: First of all, below 200 °C, there is a significant increase in thermal expansion upon heating [17]. This leads to a decrease in density of the tridymite and cristobalite grains and thus to a decrease in thermal conductivity that must be considered as a precursor of the phase transition, although the symmetries of cristobalite and tridymite still remain unchanged. Upon heating to temperatures higher than 200 °C, the situation is relatively clear for cristobalite: a phase transition occurs from the tetragonal higher-density low-temperature subpolymorph (density 2.32 g/cm³) to a cubic lower-density high-temperature subpolymorph (density 2.20 g/cm³) [52] which occupies a larger specific volume and is thus able to close pre-existing microcracks and thus to increase the thermal conductivity again. In the case of tridymite the situation is more complex, because tridymite may exist in several similar structures (subpolymorphs) that are difficult to distinguish and for which more than one phase transition may occur, but in a simplified view also here we have a transition from low-symmetry higher-density low-temperature subpolymorphs (density approximately 2.26 g/cm³) to hexagonal lower-density high-temperature subpolymorph (density approximately 2.22 g/cm³) [52]. That means, in both cases there is a volume increase of the individual grains during heating, which is generally expected to reduce the thermal conductivity,

Fig. 13. Thermal diffusivity of silica refractory as a function of temperature, measured continuously during heating and cooling.

Fig. 14. Thermal diffusivity of silicite as a function of temperature, measured continuously during heating and cooling.

Fig. 15. Thermal diffusivity of sandstone as a function of temperature, measured continuously during heating and cooling.

but only the symmetry change enables the grains to fill the original pre-existing microcracks, which increases thermal conductivity. While the former is an effect at the scale of the crystal lattice of individual grains, the latter is an effect at the scale of the microstructure of the materials as a whole.

Very important for practical applications is the comparison of the behavior of the materials during and after thermal cycling (heating and cooling). Figs. 13 through 18 show that above the highest density-changing phase transitions (i.e. the cristobalite transition for the silica refractory and the quartz transition for silicite and sandstone) the

heating and cooling branches are identical, while below these temperatures the cooling branches always exhibit lower values. This general finding must be attributed to irreversible microcracking due to thermal cycling. The consequences of this irreversible thermal-cycling-induced microcracking are especially severe for sandstone, where the temperature dependence of the thermal conductivity completely loses its aforementioned quasi-hyperbolic character and adopts an almost constant value of ~ 1 W/mK down to room temperature. There can be multiple reasons for this irreversible microcracking, e.g. the decomposition of muscovite, which can be expected at ~ 800 °C [53]. On the

Fig. 16. Thermal conductivity of silica refractory as a function of temperature, determined for heating and cooling.

Fig. 17. Thermal conductivity of silicite as a function of temperature, determined for heating and cooling.

other hand, the silica refractory and the silicite regain after cooling to room temperature a thermal conductivity value that is close to (albeit slightly smaller than) the value of the pristine material before heating. Fig. 20 shows that after repeated thermal cycling of silica refractories the room temperature values of the thermal conductivity are almost the same, i.e. the (cumulative) damage parameter defined as

$$D_k = 1 - \frac{k_{final}(20\text{ }^\circ\text{C})}{k_{initial}(20\text{ }^\circ\text{C})} \quad (23)$$

is 18.3 % after the first cycle and 17.3 % after the second cycle. In this equation $k_{initial}(20\text{ }^\circ\text{C})$ and $k_{final}(20\text{ }^\circ\text{C})$ are the initial and final values of the thermal conductivity at room temperature, respectively (i.e. the values before and after cycling).

In order to achieve a better temperature resolution, a silica refractory sample has been subjected to twofold thermal cycling with a maximum temperature of only 300 °C in the laser-flash apparatus. The results show that there is a well reproducible hysteresis of the cristobalite transition (of approximately 18 K) between heating (~210 °C) and cooling (~192

Fig. 18. Thermal conductivity of sandstone as a function of temperature, determined for heating and cooling.

Fig. 19. Overall comparison of the temperature dependence of thermal conductivity for the silica refractory, silicite and sandstone, measured continuously during heating and cooling.

°C), see Fig. 21. This hysteresis is well known in the literature and has been thoroughly investigated in the context of the temperature dependence of the elastic properties of silica refractories [9,11,12]. The results for thermal cycling to 300 °C also confirm the conclusion from Fig. 20 that the degree of damage (cumulative damage parameter) after the second cycle is almost the same as after the first cycle. Consequently, significant decreases of thermal conductivity are not expected even after further cycling. In both cases (i.e. thermal cycling to 300 and 800 °C) the degree of damage determined from the thermal conductivity is much lower than for elastic properties [16,17]. Hence, the effect of microcracks on the thermal conductivity is far weaker than on the elastic

properties. This is plausible because microcracks represent mechanical discontinuities of the material that have a detrimental effect on mechanical properties, while providing only a minor barrier to heat flux (interfacial thermal resistance).

It has to be emphasized that the results in this paper have been obtained by “dynamic” laser-flash measurements during heating and cooling (i.e. for a quasi-continuous temperature range). This is only possible because the laser pulses are very short compared to the heating and cooling rates. Very similar results could in principle be obtained by “static” laser-flash measurements (i.e. for a discrete set of temperatures), in which the sample is first heated or cooled to a certain temperature and

Fig. 20. Thermal diffusivity (left) and conductivity (right) of silica refractory measured continuously during two thermal cycles (i.e. two times heating and cooling) with maximum temperature 800 °C.

Fig. 21. Thermal diffusivity (left) and conductivity (right) of silica refractory measured continuously during two thermal cycles with maximum temperature 300 °C.

then probed by laser pulses. However, the times required for attaining thermal equilibrium of the samples (it should be recalled that the measurements are performed in vacuum because graphite sample holders are used) are so long that the temperature steps would be much too large to capture the phase transitions with adequate temperature resolution. Therefore, probing a quasi-continuous temperature range is practically impossible by “static” laser-flash measurements. Nevertheless, as shown in the Introduction (Fig. 1) for silica refractory samples of different thickness, taking account the much worse temperature resolution, the results of these “static” laser-flash measurements are very similar to the results of the “dynamic” laser-flash measurements presented in this paper. Of course, “static” laser-flash measurements are fully adequate when phase transitions are not expected.

4. Summary and conclusions

In this paper the thermal conductivity of silica refractories, as determined from laser-flash measurements, has been compared with that of silicite and sandstone. At room temperature this thermal conductivity is significantly lower than predicted by analytical relations and numerical simulations based on the phase composition and porosity, which indicates the presence of microcracks not only in the silica refractory but also (albeit to a lesser degree in the pristine state) in the silicite and the sandstone. On the other hand, direct experimental measurements of the thermal conductivity via transient plane source techniques are in good agreement with the thermal conductivity calculated from the thermal diffusivity measured by the laser-flash technique, combined with the measured bulk density and specific heat data from the literature. This supports the confidence in the reliability and accuracy of the laser-flash data in this work.

In the pristine state (i.e. before thermal cycling) the absolute room temperature values of thermal diffusivity and conductivity are lowest for silica refractories (~ 1.3 W/mK), highest for silicite (~ 6.0 W/mK), and intermediate for sandstone (~ 2.5 W/mK). This is primarily caused by the different porosities of these materials (21, 12 and < 2 %, respectively), the phase composition being of secondary importance. The temperature dependences (from room temperature to 800 °C) of the thermal diffusivity and conductivity of the silica refractory, silicite and sandstone show characteristic differences. While that of the silica refractory exhibits typical anomalies below ~ 200 °C, which are related to the phase transitions of tridymite and cristobalite, those of silicite and sandstone exhibit during heating the quasi-hyperbolic decrease that is typical for most crystalline solids. However, above ~ 200 °C the thermal conductivity of the silica refractories increases during heating and thus the difference to silicite and sandstone becomes smaller. Above the quartz transition temperature sandstone has a lower value (~ 1 W/mK) than the silica refractory (~ 1.4 – 1.6 W/mK), while the value for silicite still remains higher (~ 2 W/mK). With a further increase in temperature beyond 800 °C silica refractories can be expected to have a higher thermal conductivity than both silicite and sandstone.

The phase transitions between the subpolymorphs of the silica polymorphs (tridymite and cristobalite, or quartz) are clearly visible in the temperature dependences of thermal diffusivity and conductivity. During cooling, the thermal diffusivity and conductivity are the same as during heating, as long as the temperature is higher than the highest phase transition temperature. Below the phase transition the values diverge, but to a different degree: while the silica refractory and the silicite regain similar (albeit slightly smaller) values after cooling as before heating, in the case of sandstone the damage is so severe that the thermal conductivity retains a very low (and almost constant) value (~ 1

W/mK) during and after cooling.

A detailed view on thermal cycling to 300 °C clearly reveals the well-known hysteresis in the transition temperature of cristobalite during heating and cooling and confirms that repeated thermal cycling of silica refractories leads to slightly lower thermal diffusivity and conductivity values, but the damage effect is much less than for elastic properties.

Data availability statement: The original raw data for this paper are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14012865>.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Lucie Kotrbová: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Data curation. **Tereza Uhlřová:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Investigation. **Willi Pabst:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis,

Conceptualization. **Jana Hubáľková:** Investigation. **Miroslav Kotouček:** Resources.

Declaration of competing interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This paper was created as part of the project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004631 Materials and technologies for sustainable development within the Jan Amos Komenský Operational Program financed by the European Union and from the state budget of the Czech Republic.

Appendix A. Temperature dependence of specific heats of silica polymorphs and other mineral phases

The temperature dependence of the specific heats of silica polymorphs and other mineral phases is the necessary input information for calculating the effective specific heat of a multiphase material according to Eq. (7), which is a key information for transforming thermal diffusivities, i.e. the primary laser-flash results, into thermal conductivities according to Eq. (2). Apart from the fact that experimental data published in the literature naturally show a certain scatter, a major problem arises when materials exhibit phase transitions between low- and high-temperature polymorphs or subpolymorphs, e.g. between the low- and high-temperature modifications of quartz, tridymite and cristobalite. Fig. A1 shows the temperature dependence of the specific heat for tridymite, as measured by Thompson and Wennemer [23], together with the two-segment (discontinuous) fit listed in Salmang and Scholze [22], the relations of which are

$$c_p(T) = 0.2276 + 1.7265 \cdot 10^{-3} T \quad (\text{A1})$$

for low-tridymite (below 117 °C)

$$c_p(T) = 0.9496 + 0.1838 \cdot 10^{-3} T, \quad (\text{A2})$$

for high-tridymite (above 117 °C). It is evident that the abrupt step at 117 °C is caused by the effort to provide an approximate fit of the data measured by Thompson and Wennemer [23] but obviously the step is an artifact of the fit and not a real effect. Using this fit relation would introduce a corresponding step artefact into the temperature dependence of the thermal conductivity calculated via Eq. (2), although it is clear that the step is devoid of physical reality. Even more problematic is the situation when the phase transition temperature determined from the thermal diffusivity is shifted in comparison to that determined via the specific heat and other properties (e.g. thermal expansion or elastic constants). In this case, extrapolating the fit relations of the high-temperature phase to lower temperature or vice versa, might seem to be a good idea but this is always problematic and should only be done if the effect of the phase transition on the specific heat is small. It should be noted in passing that the experimental data by Thompson and Wennemer [23] indicate three phase transitions in tridymite (beside ~115 °C also 165 and 185 °C), which further complicates the situation. It is neither clear how sharp these discontinuities are, nor how high the singularities (maxima) would be when the temperature resolution would be higher. Therefore, in our fit we have preferred to abstain from taking into account the singularities at all, just by excluding the data in the temperature ranges 110–138 °C and 142–226 °C from fitting. In the case of cristobalite the singularity of data measured by Thompson and Wennemer [23] has been reduced to a small step in the two-segment (discontinuous) fit relations by Salmang and Scholze [22], see Fig. A2. In this case, the step is very small and for the purpose of the present paper negligible. Nevertheless, for reasons of consistency, also in this case we have performed a new fit in the same way as for tridymite, i.e. by excluding the data close to the singularity in the temperature range 217–269 °C from fitting. Figure A2 shows the temperature dependence of the specific heat for cristobalite, as measured by Thompson and Wennemer [23], together with the two-segment (discontinuous) fit listed in Salmang and Scholze [22], the relations of which are

$$c_p(T) = 0.7804 + 0.5242 \cdot 10^{-3} T - 0.1678 \cdot 10^5 / T^2 \quad (\text{A3})$$

for low-cristobalite (below 270 °C) [22],

$$c_p(T) = 1.1918 + 0.0313 \cdot 10^{-3} T - 0.6502 \cdot 10^5 / T^2 \quad (\text{A4})$$

for high-cristobalite (above 270 °C) [22].

Fig. A1. Temperature dependence of the specific heat data of tridymite according to Thompson and Wennemer [23], two-segment (discontinuous) fit according to Salmang and Scholze [22] and one-segment (continuous) fit used in the present work, see Eq. (13) in the main text.

Fig. A2. Temperature dependence of the specific heat of cristobalite according to Thompson and Wennemer [23], two-segment (discontinuous) fit according to Salmang and Scholze [22], and one-segment (continuous) fit used in the present work, see Eq. (14) in the main text.

Fig. A3 shows the temperature dependence of the thermal conductivity of silica refractories, calculated according to Eq. (2) from the thermal diffusivity shown in Fig. 20 in the main text, but with Eqs. A1–A4 as fits for the specific heats of tridymite and cristobalite instead of Eqs. (13) and (14) in the main text. It is evident that at 117 °C there is a step-wise discontinuity in the thermal conductivity that has no counterpart in the thermal diffusivity (even if shifted from 117 to ~90 °C, where there is an observable kink in the temperature dependence of thermal diffusivity) and must therefore be considered as a computational artefact. Figs. A4–A6 show the temperature dependence of the specific heat for pseudowollastonite, quartz, muscovite, microcline and hematite.

Fig. A3. Temperature dependence of the thermal conductivity of silica refractories, calculated according to Eq. (2) from the thermal diffusivity shown in the left hand side of Fig. 20, but with Eqs. (A1) and (A2) as fits for the specific heats of tridymite and cristobalite instead of Eqs. (13) and 14 in the main text; note the step-wise discontinuity at 117 °C, which has to be considered as a computational artefact.

Fig. A4. Temperature dependence of the specific heat of pseudowollastonite according to Parks and Kelley [24] and our fit to these values, see Eq. (15) in the main text.

Fig. A5. Temperature dependence of the specific heat of quartz according to Chase [54] and two-segment (discontinuous) fit according to Salmang and Scholze [22], see Eqs. (17) and (18) in the main text.

Fig. A6. Temperature dependence of the specific heat of muscovite, microcline and hematite according to [45–47] and our fit to these values, see Eqs. (19)–(22) in the main text.

References

- [1] A. Majdič, G. Routschka, Feuerfeste Baustoffe für den Hochofenwinderhitzer im Spiegel der Literatur (Refractories for the hot blast stove as reflected in the literature., in German), *Keram. Z.* 23 (10) (1971) 1–9.
- [2] F. Tomšů, et al., Thermomechanisches Verhalten von Silicasteinen in Winderhitzern, *Stahl und Eisen* 92 (4) (1972) 157–161.
- [3] Staroň J., Tomšů F.: *Žiaruvzdorné materiály – Výroba, vlastnosti a použitie* (Refractory Materials – Productions, Properties and Application, in Slovakian), pp. 104–120, 218–221, 364–367. Slovomag Lubeník /Slovenské magnezitové závody Jelšava / Keramika Košice, 2000.
- [4] M. Kotouček, K. Lang, L. Vašica, S. Dvorák, L. Nevřivová, Ohříváče vysokopečního větru (OV) – Dinas v OV a jeho vývojový trend (Hot blast stoves (HBS) – Silica refractories in HBS and their development trends, in Czech), in: *Sborník přednášek Hutní keramika* (Conference Proceedings of Ceramics for Metallurgy, in Czech), Tanager s.r.o. / Technical University Ostrava, 2013, pp. 35–41.
- [5] M. Henek, J. Kutzendörfer, K. Lang, Š. Palčo, F. Tomšů. *Žárovzdorné materiály díl VIII – Použití žárovzdorných materiálů* (Refractories Part 8 – Application of Refractories, in Czech), Silikátová Společnost České republiky (Czech Ceramic Society), Prague, 2016, pp. 40–43.
- [6] X. Zhang, Y. Li, Y. Cui, Z. Tian, L. Sun, C. Ma, Y. Sun, Corrosion mechanism of silica bricks containing high amorphous for hot stoves, *Ceram. Int.* 49 (2023) 40746–40753.
- [7] Wieland K.: Feuerfeste Werkstoffe für Regeneratoren und Rekuperatoren (Refractories for regenerators and recuperators, in German), pp. 55–71 in Hüttentechnische Vereinigung der Deutschen Glasindustrie (ed.): *Feuerfeste Werkstoffe für die Glasindustrie und deren Prüfung* (Refractories for the Glass Industry and Their Testing, in German). Verlag der Deutschen Glastechnischen Gesellschaft, Frankfurt 1998.
- [8] Bauer R.A.: Temperaturmessung (Temperature measurement, in German), pp. 1–22 in Hüttentechnische Vereinigung der Deutschen Glasindustrie (ed.): *Einsatz von Messtechnik beim Glasschmelzprozess* (Application of measuring techniques in the glass melting process, in German). Verlag der Deutschen Glastechnischen Gesellschaft, Frankfurt 1996.

- [9] W. Pabst, E. Gregorová, J. Kutzendörfer, Elastic anomalies in tridymite- and cristobalite-based silica materials, *Ceram. Int.* 40 (2014) 4207–4211.
- [10] P. Pilate, V. Lardot, F. Cambier, E. Brochen, Contribution to the understanding of the high temperature behavior and of the compressive creep behavior of silica refractory materials, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 35 (2015) 813–822.
- [11] E. Gregorová, M. Černý, W. Pabst, L. Esposito, C. Zanelli, J. Hamáček, J. Kutzendörfer, Temperature dependence of Young's modulus of silica refractories, *Ceram. Int.* 41 (2015) 1129–1138.
- [12] W. Pabst, E. Gregorová, J. Klouček, A. Kloučková, P. Zemenová, M. Kohoutková, I. Sedlářová, K. Lang, M. Kotouček, L. Nevřivová, D. Všianský, High-temperature Young's moduli and dilatation behavior of silica refractories, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 36 (2016) 209–220.
- [13] E. Gregorová, W. Pabst, P. Diblíková, V. Nečina, Temperature dependence of damping in silica refractories measured via the impulse excitation technique, *Ceram. Int.* 44 (2018) 8363–8373.
- [14] K. Andreev, V. Tadaion, Q. Zhu, W. Wang, Y. Yin, T. Tonnesen, Thermal and mechanical cyclic tests and fracture mechanics parameters as indicators of thermal shock resistance – case study on silica refractories, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 39 (2019) 1650–1659.
- [15] Y. Yin, S. Jin, Q. Zhu, Y. Dai, Y. Li, Z. Xia, Thermal expansion and Young's modulus evolution of fused silica and crystalline silica-containing materials, *Int. J. Appl. Ceram. Technol.* 20 (2023) 1875–1886.
- [16] E. Gregorová, L. Kotrbová, W. Pabst, Thermal cycling damage of silica refractories for high-temperature thermal energy storage (HT-TES) – Can it be healed? *Open Ceram* 19 (2024) 100658.
- [17] E. Gregorová, W. Pabst, P. Šimonová, V. Nečina, L. Kotrbová, P. Bezdička, J. Hubálková, G. Schmidt, C.G. Aneziris, I. Sedlářová, M. Kotouček, Temperature dependence of Young's modulus, damping and dilatation during repeated thermal cycling of silica refractories for high-temperature thermal energy storage (TES), *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 45 (2025) 116946.
- [18] S. Yang, X.H. Zhang, H. Hu, X. Liu, B. Chen, Performance of high thermal conductivity dense silica bricks and their high thermal conductivity mechanism, *Chin. Refract.* 31 (2022) 30–34.
- [19] L. Kotrbová, T. Uhlířová, W. Pabst, Thermal conductivity of silica refractories determined via the laser-flash technique – From modeling to experimental issues, in: *Sborník přednášek Hutní keramika* (Conference Proceedings of Ceramics for Metallurgy). Tanger s.r.o. /Technical University Ostrava, Ostrava, 2024, pp. 24–30.
- [20] Kotora J., Kutzendörfer J., Paľčo Š., Tomsů F.: *Žárovzdorné materiály díl IX – Fyzikální konstanty a jakostní parametry žárovzdorných materiálů* (Refractories Part 9 – Physical Constants and Quality Parameters of Refractories, in Czech), pp. 39 and 62. Silikátová Společnost České republiky (Czech Ceramic Society), Prague 2013.
- [21] M. Kunugi, N. Soga, H. Sawa, A. Konoshi, Thermal conductivity of cristobalite, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 55 (1972) 580.
- [22] H. Salmang, H. Scholze, *Keramik – Teil 1* (Ceramics – Part 1, in German), Springer, Berlin, 1982.
- [23] A.B. Thompson, M. Wennemer, Heat capacities and inversions in tridymite, cristobalite, and tridymite-cristobalite mixed phases, *Am. Miner.* 64 (1979) 1018–1026.
- [24] G.S. Parks, K.K. Kelley, The heat capacity of calcium silicate, *J. Phys. Chem.* 30 (1926) 1175–1178.
- [25] I. Fanderlik, *Silica Glass and Its Application*, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1991.
- [26] W. Pabst, E. Gregorová, Elastic properties of silica polymorphs – a review, *Ceram. Silik.* 57 (2013) 167–184.
- [27] L. Kotrbová, *Tepelná vodivost keramických materiálů, hornin a stavebních materiálů* (Thermal Conductivity of Ceramic Materials, Rocks and Building Materials, in Czech), Master thesis. UCT Prague, 2022.
- [28] H.M. Rietveld, A profile refinement method for nuclear and magnetic structures, *J. Appl. Cryst.* 2 (1969) 65–71.
- [29] T. Degen, M. Sadki, E. Bron, U. König, G. Nénert, The HighScore Suite, *J. Powder Diffract.* 29 (S2) (2014) S13–S18.
- [30] PDF-5+ database. International Centre for Diffraction Data, Newtown Square 2024.
- [31] I.C. Madsen, N.V.Y. Scarlett, A. Kern, Description and survey of methodologies for the determination of amorphous content via X-ray powder diffraction, *Z. Kristallogr.* 226 (2011) 944–955.
- [32] ASTM E1461-01. Standard Test Method for Thermal Diffusivity of Solids by the Flash Method, ASTM International, West Conshohocken, 2001.
- [33] W.J. Parker, R.J. Jenkins, C.P. Butler, G.L. Abbott, Thermal diffusivity measurements using the laser flash technique, *J. Appl. Phys.* 32 (9) (1961) 1679–1684.
- [34] L. Duszka, Combined solution of the simultaneous heat loss and finite pulse corrections with the laser flash method, *High Temp. High Press.* 27–28 (1996) 467–473.
- [35] ASTM D7984-16: Standard Test Method for Measurement of Thermal Effusivity of Fabrics Using a Modified Transient Plane Source (MTPS) Instrument of Solids by the Flash Method, ASTM International, West Conshohocken 2016.
- [36] Pabst W., Hostaša J.: Thermal conductivity of ceramics: from monolithic to multiphase, from dense to porous, from micro to nano, pp. 1-112 in Wythers M.C. (ed.): *Advances in Materials Science Research – Volume 7*. 315 pp. Nova Science Publishers, New York 2012.
- [37] Pabst W., Uhlířová T., Hříbalová S., Nečina V.: Rigorous bounds, model predictions and mixture rules for the effective thermal conductivity of multiphase and porous ceramics – from theory to practice, Chapter 1 (pp. 1-131) in Sohel Murshed S. M. (ed.): *An Essential Guide to Thermal Conductivity*. 376 pp. Nova Science Publishers, New York 2021.
- [38] A. Wiegmann, K.P. Bube, The explicit-jump immersed interface method: finite difference methods for PDEs with piecewise smooth solutions, *SIAM J. Numer. Anal.* 37 (2000) 827–862.
- [39] A. Wiegmann, A. Zemitis, A Fast Explicit Jump Harmonic Averaging Solver for the Effective Heat Conductivity of Composite Materials. Technical Report No. 94. Fraunhofer-Institut für Techno- und Wirtschaftsmathematik (Fraunhofer ITWM), Kaiserslautern (2006).
- [40] J. Chojnacki, *Základy chemické a fyzikální krystalografie* (Fundamentals of Chemical and Physical Crystallography, in Czech). Academia, Prague, 1979.
- [41] K. Horai, Thermal conductivity of rock-forming minerals, *J. Geophys. Res.* 76 (1971) 1278–1308.
- [42] W.H. Diment, H.R. Pratt, *Thermal Conductivity of Some Rock-Forming Minerals – A Tabulation*. Geological Survey Open File Report 88-690, US Department of the Interior, Washington, 1988.
- [43] Z. Hashin, S. Shtrikman, Conductivity of polycrystals, *Phys. Rev.* 130 (1963) 129–133.
- [44] J.E. Molyneux, Effective permittivity of a polycrystalline dielectric, *J. Math. Phys.* 11 (1970) 1172–1184.
- [45] K.M. Krupka, R.A. Robie, B.S. Hemingway, High-temperature heat capacities of corundum, periclase, anorthite, $\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8$ glass, muscovite, pyrophyllite, KAlSi_3O_8 glass, grossular, and $\text{NaAlSi}_3\text{O}_8$ glass, *Am. Miner.* 64 (1–2) (1979) 86–101.
- [46] B.S. Hemingway, K.M. Krupka, R.A. Robie, Heat capacities of the alkali feldspars between 350 and 1000 K from differential scanning calorimetry, the thermodynamic functions of the alkali feldspars from 298.15 to 1500 K, and the reaction quartz + jadeite = analbite, *Am. Miner.* 66 (11–12) (1981) 1202–1215.
- [47] Robie R.A., Hemingway B.S.: *Thermodynamic Properties of Minerals and Related Substances at 298.15 K and 1 bar (105Pascals) Pressure and at Higher Temperatures* (US Geol. Surv. Bull. 2131). US Government Printing Office, Washington 1995.
- [48] A. Shyam, J. Muth, E. Lara-Curzio, The elastic properties of β -eucryptite in the glassy and microcracked state, *Acta Mater* 60 (2012) 5867–5876.
- [49] G. Bruno, M. Kachanov, On modeling of microstresses and microcracking generated by cooling of polycrystalline ceramics, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 33 (2013) 1995–2005.
- [50] A. Shyam, G. Bruno, T.R. Watkins, A. Pandey, E. Lara-Curzio, C.M. Parish, R. J. Stafford, The effect of porosity and microcracking on the thermomechanical properties of cordierite, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 35 (2015) 4557–4566.
- [51] V. Buljak, G. Bruno, Numerical modeling of thermally induced microcracking in porous ceramics – An approach using cohesive elements, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 38 (2018) 4099–4108.
- [52] W. Pabst, E. Gregorová, Elastic properties of silica polymorphs – a review, *Ceram. Silik.* 57 (2013) 167–184.
- [53] G.L. Gaines, W. Vedder, Dehydroxylation of muscovite, *Nature* 4918 (1964) 495.
- [54] Chase M.W.: *NIST-JANAF Thermochemical Tables* (4th edition). National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), Gaithersburg 1998.